

UPC Catalog Evaluation

Thank you for participating in the practical activity using the UPC Catalogue! We would now like to learn a little more about you and about your experience using the catalog. To this end, we have prepared a questionnaire that takes approximately 5 to 7 minutes to complete. Your participation is anonymous and voluntary, and your feedback helps us continuously improve the catalog.

Profile information

1. What was your level of familiarity with topics related to personal data protection (such as LGPD/GDPR)? *

- I had never had contact with the topic.
- I had heard about it, but never studied it.
- I had formally studied the topic (e.g., in other courses, training programs, or through legislation), but never applied it.
- I have applied personal data protection in software development.
- I currently perform or have performed a specific role related to personal data protection (controller, processor, DPO, consultant, auditor, etc.).

2. What is your academic background? *

- I do not have an academic degree.
- I am currently pursuing an undergraduate degree.
- I have an undergraduate degree.
- I have a specialization degree.
- I am currently pursuing a master's degree.
- I have a master's degree.
- I am currently pursuing a doctoral degree.
- I have a doctoral degree.

Other: _____

3. What is your area of education? *

- Information Technology.
- Law.
- Design.

Other: _____

4. Have you worked or do you currently work professionally in software development or related areas (e.g., developer, analyst, product owner, UX, testing, technical support, databases, consultant)? *

- I have no professional experience.

- () Less than 1 year of professional experience.
- () Between 1 and 2 years of professional experience.
- () Between 2 and 5 years of professional experience.
- () More than 5 years of professional experience.

Other: _____

Evaluating the guidelines

Please consider the organization and content of the guidelines.

1. The guidelines facilitated the proposal of improvements to the analyzed system. *

Strongly disagree Strongly agree
 1 2 3 4 5

2. It was easy to identify guidelines related to the identified problems. *

Strongly disagree Strongly agree
 1 2 3 4 5

3. The guidelines are suitable for real-world digital system contexts. *

Strongly disagree Strongly agree
 1 2 3 4 5

4. Using the guidelines facilitated understanding how legal principles and rights related to personal data protection are applied. *

Strongly disagree Strongly agree
 1 2 3 4 5

5. I feel that I am now able to develop better digital systems by considering data protection practices. *

Strongly disagree Strongly agree
 1 2 3 4 5

Evaluating usability (SUS)

1. I think that I would like to use this catalogue frequently. *

Strongly disagree Strongly agree
 1 2 3 4 5

2. I found the catalogue unnecessarily complex. *

Strongly disagree Strongly agree
 1 2 3 4 5

3. I thought the catalogue was easy to use. *

Strongly disagree ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 Strongly agree

4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this catalogue. *

Strongly disagree ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 Strongly agree

5. I found the various functions in this catalogue were well integrated. *

Strongly disagree ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 Strongly agree

6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in the catalogue. *

Strongly disagree ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 Strongly agree

7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use the catalogue very quickly. *

Strongly disagree ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 Strongly agree

8. I found the catalogue very cumbersome to use. *

Strongly disagree ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 Strongly agree

9. I felt very confident using the catalogue. *

Strongly disagree ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 Strongly agree

10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the catalogue. *

Strongly disagree ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 Strongly agree

Would you like to leave any comments about using the catalogue, your experience with the activity, or suggestions for improvement?
